

11. Формуюча головка з регулюємим перепадом тиску [Текст]: пат. 102027 Україна: МПК В29С47/12 / Носко С.В., Шевчук О.А.; власник

Націон. техн. ун-т України «Київський політехн. ін-т. №102027; заявл. 20.01.15; опубл. 12.10.15, Бюл. №19.- Зс.

ENERGY-SAVING "PYROLYSIS OVEN" AND ITS MAIN ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

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Abstract

This article presents methods for determining the energy efficiency of pyrolysis furnaces used in heating systems, analysis of the efficiency, advantages and disadvantages of pyrolysis furnaces.

Keywords: Pyrolysis, heating system, furnace, efficiency, energy efficiency.

Introduction

It is known that the pyrolysis process is used in the chemical industry as the main technology for the production of products, as an energy-saving technology for heating buildings and structures in housing and communal services. In the oil industry, pyrolysis is the only technology for the separation of some products, but it is the process that ensures the optimal combustion of combustible products in heating devices. The complex gas released during the pyrolysis process was actively used as a fuel for internal combustion engines in the 30s and 60s of the last century. Today, pyrolysis gas is still used as a fuel for forestry vehicles. Pyrolysis furnaces for heating homes on individual farms are notable for their ease of operation and low fuel consumption. In Central Asia, pyrolysis furnaces are almost never used in individual systems of households and small enterprises and institutions. In areas with limited natural gas resources, complexes of pyrolysis furnaces and gas generators operating on this energy-saving technology can solve the problem of electricity and natural gas shortages. Therefore, the study of these pyrolysis furnaces and gas generators can be considered a topical issue.

Research method

We use process analysis to select a research method.

A pyrolysis furnace is the main energy source of the heating system, its energy efficiency is determined by determining the consumption of the "conventional fuel unit", calculating the energy balance of the heated object, and integrated assessment of the amount of energy required to maintain this energy balance in changing natural conditions methods. The final integral is needed to determine the energy capacity of the pyrolysis furnace (in terms of heat). It is also necessary to take into account the heat and electricity consumed by the control system.

It is known that it is not possible to directly measure the heat energy given off by a fuel product during combustion, this energy can only be found by multiplying the relative combustion heat of that fuel by the weight of the fuel. Typically, the relative heat of combustion of the fuel is obtained from references and different GOSTs for different fuels, for example, GOST 10062-75 - for natural gas, 21261-91 - for liquid petroleum products, 147-95 - for coal, for peat and others. However, given that the composition of the fuel

used in practice is constantly changing, and that the heat energy that this composition produces during combustion also changes, the amount of energy calculated is approximate. Nevertheless, we need to evaluate the energy efficiency of the pyrolysis furnace. To solve this problem, experimentally determine the weight of the energy-supplying fuel that provides the energy balance of the heated object and calculate the energy consumption by multiplying the relative combustion heat of that amount of fuel by the weight of the fuel, and finally, the ratio of energies can be calculated. The size obtained by this method depends on the heating system tested, but mainly on the energy efficiency of the furnace under test.

Of course, an artificial heating system can be used as the object of the above experiment, but it is preferable to use a real object because this experiment is associated with much higher energy consumption.

The difference between pyrolysis furnaces and conventional furnaces is that the combustion process in this furnace consists of two stages, in the first stage the coking produces solid residues of fuel and gas, and in the second stage, the solid residues of the separated gas and fuel are completely burned.

This type of stove burns the wood completely and produces very little ash. As a result, the fuel burns in the pyrolysis furnace for a long time. In practice, the ash from such furnaces is cleaned once every few days.

In addition, the useful life of any heating system is several decades, during which time it is desirable to use the literature data to account for large-scale changes in the operating modes of the heating system due to climate change.

So, we choose the data analysis method as the research method.

According to the manufacturers, medium-capacity (10-20 kW) furnaces installed in a 100 m² apartment building can burn 10-12 hours of fuel per refill. Daily fuel consumption can be 10-11 kg of solid wood. Compared to conventional furnaces, this is 2 or more times the fuel-saving efficiency.

Depending on the moisture content of the fuel, this efficiency varies widely:

burning 1 kg of wood with a moisture content of 20% - 4 kW

burning 1 kg of wood with a moisture content of 50% - provides 2 kW of power.

Advantages of pyrolysis furnaces:

- High fuel efficiency due to long and complete combustion
- Environmental safety, which emits very little smoke, mainly SO and water vapor, resulting in clean and dry smoke ducts.
- The fuel heats up very quickly.
- Has a high efficiency (85% - 90%).
- Ability to operate in a large power range (5% to 100% of maximum power).
- Possibility to connect to any heating system - with natural circulation and forced circulation.

- Possibility to use different types of fuel, solid wood, liquid fuel ...
 - Ease of use, once a day wood burning and once a few days ash removal.
- These ovens have the following disadvantages:
- The size is too big.
 - Need a place to store firewood.
 - Water pump, fan, and thermocouple are required for proper operation and control, which in turn creates an electrical connection.
 - Condensate can build up in the smoke path, so the smoke path needs heat protection

Figure 1. Construction of a long-burning pyrolysis furnace

Pyrolysis furnaces are divided into two depending on the type of smoke:

- natural smoke extraction;
- Compulsory smoking.

Natural smoke extraction is created using a high smoke extraction pipe. Forced smoke extraction is

generated using an electric motor fan. Forced smoke weighing furnace is more efficient but depends on electricity.

The following are the disadvantages and advantages of forced and natural smoke kilns:

Smoke	Advantages	Disadvantages
Compulsory	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The combustion chamber and the heating system heat up quickly 2. Accelerates the transition to pyrolysis 3. Combustion products come out of the oven quickly 4. Pyrolysis and combustion process is controlled automatically 5. The combustion time of the fuel is large 	Depends on electricity
natural	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Relatively easy to use 2. breakdown are rare 3. The price is much cheaper 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Needs to be cleaned relatively often 2. The installation cost is high

Conclusion:

With the advantages and disadvantages listed above, these stoves are the second most energy-efficient after gas heating systems.

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